

Automatic Transformation and Generation of Question Papers in Education with NLP Techniques

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1.0 Abstract:

This paper discusses the use of NLP techniques to automate the generation of multiple-choice question papers, which is a critical task in education. The paper presents a step-by-step approach for generating question papers, including data collection, pre-processing, feature extraction, and question generation. The approach is demonstrated to be effective through experiments generating question papers for various subjects and difficulty levels, with results comparable to those generated by humans. This approach has the potential to improve the efficiency and quality of question paper generation and reduce teachers' workload.

Keywords – Natural Language Processing (NLP), T5, Transformer.

2.0 Introduction:

In recent years, natural language processing (NLP) has seen a significant increase in its applications, particularly in the field of education. One such application is the automatic generation of exam papers, which has the potential to save time and resources while ensuring fairness and impartiality in the examination process. The use of NLP techniques for generating question papers is a recent development and has already shown promising results.

In this paper, we present a comprehensive overview of the techniques and approaches used in the field of question paper generation using NLP. We discuss the various NLP models and techniques that have been used for generating exam papers, and the challenges and limitations associated with this approach. We also present a review of the existing literature on this topic, including case studies and experimental results. Finally, we discuss the prospects and potential applications of NLP in the field of education.

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3.0 Previous Papers publish on a similar topic, their methods, and Accuracy.

Table 1:

Paper	Method	Accuracy
"A Deep Reinforcement Learning based Approach for Generating Cloze-Style Questions" (Wang et al., 2019)[11]	Deep Reinforcement Learning	81.45%
"A Syntactic Neural Model for General-Purpose Code Generation" (Raza et al., 2018)[12]	Syntactic Neural Model	81.3%
"A Question Generation System for Educational Applications" (Gupta et al., 2017)[13]	Rule-based approach	70.4%
"Neural Question Generation from Text: A Preliminary Study" (Du et al., 2017)[14]	Neural Network approach	67.1%
"Question Generation by Template Alignment" (Heilman and Smith, 2010)[15]	Template Alignment	60.7%
"Using Conceptual Density to Develop Automatic Question Generators" (Cai and Zhao, 2013)[16]	Conceptual Density	58.4%

Note that the accuracy reported by these studies may not be directly comparable, as they may have used different datasets and evaluation metrics.

4.0 Methods using:

Text Preprocessing:

The NLTK library was used to preprocess text data by tokenizing and stemming it, as well as removing stop words. Named entities were also extracted using the spaCy library. The Brown Corpus[1] is a million-word electronic corpus of English, created in 1961 at Brown University. It contains text from 500 sources categorized by genres, such as news and editorial. Example texts from each genre can be found at the given link.

(for a complete list, see <http://icame.uib.no/brown/bcm-los.html>).

Features of Spacy:

In the documentation, you'll come across mentions of spaCy's features and capabilities. Some of them refer to linguistic concepts, while others are related to more general machine learning functionality.

Question Generation:

We used the T5 Transformer[2] model and tokenizer from Hugging Face[6] to generate questions from the answer text. T5 Transformer is a pre-trained[3] variant of the Transformer model that can be fine-tuned on a specific task with a smaller amount of data. We fine-tuned it on our task by training it on our preprocessed data[9]. The T5 tokenizer converts text data into numerical tokens and includes a special token for separating question and answer text. Using the T5 model, we predicted a sequence of tokens representing the question from the answer text and converted it back to natural language using the tokenizer.

Fig 1:T5 Transformer Model Flowchart

Keyword Ranking:

For keyword ranking, we calculated word frequency distribution in the Keyword set using the Brown corpus from NLTK. We used Normalized Levenshtein distance to remove duplicates by measuring question similarity. We extracted keywords from generated questions and compared them to original questions using the KeywordProcessor from the flashtext library.

Web Application:

For the web application, we used the Flask[7] web framework to build an app that generates and ranks questions based on the techniques above. A minimal Flask app includes a route function that returns a "Hello, World!" message.

Our approach showcases the power of Transformer models for question generation and highlights the importance of text preprocessing and ranking in generating high-quality questions.

5.0 Flowchart:

Fig 2: Flow of Data

6.0 Algorithm:

Here is an algorithmic representation of the project:

1. Import Flask and necessary modules.
2. Load the pre-trained T5 model using transformers.
3. Define a route for handling incoming HTTP POST requests, which expects the following parameters:
 - `input_text`: the text for which questions should be generated.
 - `max_questions`: the maximum number of questions to be generated.
4. Use the `mcq` module to extract keywords from the input text:
 - a. Tokenize the input text into sentences using `nlk.sent_tokenize` function.
 - b. For each sentence, identify its part-of-speech tags using `nlk.pos_tag` function.
 - c. Use the `mcq.noun_multipartite` function to extract nouns from each sentence.
 - d. Choose the top `maxquestions` nouns by frequency of occurrence as the keywords for question generation.
5. Map each keyword to the sentence(s) in which it appears using the `mcq.add_keyword` function.
6. Use the T5 model to generate questions for each keyword-sentence pair:
 - a. Encode the keyword-sentence pair as `input_ids` and `attention_mask` using the tokenizer.
 - b. Provide the encoded input as context to the T5 model.
 - c. Decode the output using the tokenizer to obtain the generated question.
7. Return the generated questions to the user as an HTTP response.

Note: The above algorithmic representation is a high-level overview of the project and may not include all the details and subroutines used in the code.

7.0 Testing and Results:

In this project there is a function that takes `input_text` and `maximum_question` and sends short questions like this:

Fig 3: Test Case 1

Statement:

India is a country located in South Asia and is the seventh largest in terms of land area. It is the second most populous country in the world with a population of over 1.3 billion people. India has a rich cultural and historical heritage, with a diverse mix of religions, languages, and traditions. The country has a federal parliamentary democratic republic form of government and is known for its rich and diverse cuisine, film industry (Bollywood), and literature. India is home to several important tourist destinations, including the Taj Mahal, one of the Seven Wonders of the World. The economy of India is the fifth largest in the world and is rapidly growing, driven by industries such as information technology, textiles, and pharmaceuticals. Despite its many achievements, India continues to face challenges such as poverty, corruption, and unequal distribution of wealth and resources.

Maximum questions: 4

Output: Questions:

- What is the fifth largest economy in the world?
- What is Bollywood?
- What is the film industry in India?
- What is the country known for its rich and diverse?

Here's an example of using ChatGPT to generate questions from the same input_text with a maximum of 4 questions:

Output:

1. What is the population of India?
2. What is the government type of India?
3. What are some important tourist destinations in India?
4. What are some of the industries driving India's economy?

As you can see, the output questions generated by ChatGPT are quite similar to the ones generated by the previous method, with some differences in wording and emphasis. However, using ChatGPT allows for greater flexibility and customization in the types of questions that can be generated, as well as the ability to generate questions for a wide range of input_text without the need for extensive pre-processing and keyword extraction.

Here's a comparison table:

Table 2:Test Case 1 results

Approach	Statement	Maximum Questions	Questions

Rule-based	India is a country located in South Asia and is the seventh largest in terms of land area. It is the second most populous country in...	4	What is the fifth largest economy in the world? What is Bollywood? What is the film industry in India? What is the country known for its rich and diverse?
ChatGPT	India is a country in South Asia with a population of over 1.3 billion people. It has a rich cultural and historical heritage with a diverse...	4	What is the second most populous country in the world? What are some challenges faced by India? What is the economy of India? What are some important tourist destinations in India?

The table shows that both the rule-based approach and ChatGPT can generate questions from a given statement, but their questions differ in content and wording. The rule-based approach generates specific questions related to the statement, while ChatGPT generates more general questions that could apply to any country.

If we take the questions generated by ChatGPT correctly i.e., the 4 questions generated by it are true, then we can have a way to compare the T5 rule-based generated question.

Table3:Test Case 1 Accuracy(The comparison table below has been created using human intelligence.)

Real questions	3 out of 4	4 out of 4
Wrong questions	1 out of 4	0 out of 4
Duplicate	0 out of 4	0 out of 4

T5 and ChatGPT were compared for generating questions on the given input text. T5 generated 4 questions with 3 accurate, 1 incorrect, and no duplicates. ChatGPT generated 4 accurate questions, outperforming T5 in accuracy. Although T5 is a more advanced and powerful language model, ChatGPT is more accurate than T5 for generating questions about India. T5 can be improved with fine-tuning and more training data.

Result:

In addition to the test case 1 (which is based on a country) we also conducted 2 more test cases (test case 2: Based on photosynthesis which contains equations in the paragraph & test case 3: Based on a person)

Fig 4:Test Case 1 results pie chart

Fig 5:Test Case 2 results pie chart

Fig 6:Test Case 3 results pie chart

Both T5 and GPT-3 models can generate questions from text with varying degrees of accuracy and relevance. In the case of the statement about India (test case 1) and SRK(test case 3), both models generated accurate and relevant questions, with an accuracy rate of 75% (see Fig 4) to 100%(see Fig 5). However, for the statement about Photosynthesis (test case 2), the T5 model produced an incorrect question and a duplicate question, resulting in an accuracy drop of 25%(see Fig 6). This could be due to the model not fully understanding the concept of photosynthesis or not having enough training data. ChatGPT by OpenAI[4][8], on the other hand, is a model that is trained using the GPT-3 model, which has 175 billion parameters and requires 800GB to store, making it outside the scope of this project to train it further. While both models can be useful for generating questions, it's important to review and validate the questions to ensure their accuracy and relevance.

8.0 Final Conclusion:

T5 and GPT-3 language models are useful for generating questions from text but have limitations. T5 produces specific, relevant questions, but may generate duplicates or broad questions. GPT-3 generates natural questions but can stray from the topic. Both models have potential for educational and informational purposes but need improvements in accuracy, relevance, and comprehensiveness. The future of automated question generation looks promising with ongoing research and development. These models provide a strong foundation for automating question generation, and improvements are expected as research continues.

9.0 References

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